
Diaspora Dynamics and Diplomatic Discord: The 2023 Canada-India Rift and its Broader Implications in International Relations

Faysal Amin

Department of Pali and Buddhist Studies, University of Dhaka

Abstract

This paper tries to go deeper into the intricate dynamics of Canada-India relations, especially in light of the recent assassination of Hardeep Singh Nijjar, a prominent Sikh leader in Canada. Nijjar's death has led to a significant diplomatic fallout between the two nations, with both sides levying serious accusations against each other. This incident is situated against the backdrop of the Khalistan movement, which calls for a separate Sikh homeland in India, and the substantial Sikh diaspora in Canada. The paper traces the historical context of Sikh representation in Canada and its implications on Canada-India bilateral relations. It further examines the immediate diplomatic and economic repercussions stemming from Nijjar's assassination, including the suspension of trade treaties and the postponement of trade missions. The involvement of the "Five Eyes" intelligence alliance adds another layer of complexity to the unfolding scenario. Drawing parallels with other diaspora-driven foreign policy decisions, the research underscores the significant influence diasporic communities can exert on international relations. The study concludes by offering potential pathways for resolution, emphasizing the importance of constructive dialogue and collaboration. As Canada and India navigate these turbulent waters, the broader implications of this incident on international diplomacy in our interconnected world are highlighted, offering lessons for future engagements.

Keywords: Religious Nationalism, International Politics, Hardeep Singh Nijjar, Canada-India Relations, Bilateral Tensions

1 Introduction

In an era characterized by rapid globalization, the resurgence of nationalism rooted in religious beliefs emerges as a counter-narrative, influencing global politics in profound ways. India, with its rich tapestry of religions, languages, and cultures, offers a compelling case study on this interplay between religious nationalism and international politics. India's tryst with religious nationalism is not a recent phenomenon [1]. Since its inception as an independent nation, the country has grappled with the delicate balance between its secular constitutional commitments and the pull of majoritarian religious sentiments. The founding fathers, led by Jawaharlal Nehru, envisioned a secular India where the state would maintain a "principled distance" from all religions, ensuring every citizen's right to faith while preventing religious encroachment into governance [2, 3]. Yet, the last few decades have witnessed the steady erosion of this Nehruvian secular ideal, replaced by a more assertive and politically dominant form of Hindu nationalism. This shift has been catalyzed by various factors, including

¹Corresponding author: faysalamin1@gmail.com

political opportunism, accusations of minority appeasement, and the genuine desire among segments of the population to see India recognized as a Hindu *Rashtra* or nation.

As the world's largest democracy, with nearly 900 million eligible voters participating in its seventeenth general election in 2019, India's political trajectory is not just a domestic affair [4]; it has significant ramifications for the global order. The rise of the Bharatiya Janata Party (BJP) in India is emblematic of this shift. Historically rooted in Hindu nationalism, the party's ascent to power has been meteoric. In 2014, the BJP, led by Prime Minister Narendra Modi, secured a mandate that few anticipated [5]. Despite earning only 31% of the nationwide vote, the party clinched 282 seats out of the 543 available, revealing a deep-seated change in India's political landscape. This ascendancy of the BJP is intertwined with a broader ideological shift [6]. Hindu nationalism, often referred to as "Hindutva," has moved from the political fringes to become a central element of India's contemporary political discourse [7]. Yet, as secularism's reputation sours due to various factors, including accusations of minority appeasement and opportunism, the BJP's rise brings forth questions about India's long-standing commitment to secularism. The BJP's ideological hegemony, built on the twin pillars of electoral dominance and a robust ideology, has redefined Indian politics. Their vision of a "New India" interweaves nationalistic fervor with Hindu majoritarian ideals, subtly conflating nationalism with Hindutva. This conflation has significant implications not just domestically but also in shaping India's posture on the global stage. Prime Minister Modi's foreign policy ambitions, aimed at recapturing India's civilizational greatness, reflects this blend of Hindu nationalism and international politics. From initiatives like Buddhist diplomacy to using Hindu sociocultural terms in global platforms such as the Paris Climate Change Conference in 2015, the imprint of religious nationalism is evident. As India stands at the crossroads of its political future, with religion deeply entrenched in its political landscape, it becomes imperative to understand the implications of this religious nationalism on its international politics. On the global stage, the implications of India's religious nationalism are vast and multifaceted. As India positions itself as a major global player, its domestic religious narratives inevitably spill over into its international engagements. Whether it's in the realm of trade, diplomacy, or strategic alliances, the undercurrents of Hindu nationalism influence India's choices and its interactions with other nations. This has led to both opportunities and challenges. While India's unique blend of modernity and tradition, driven by its religious cultural heritage, offers it a distinctive voice in global forums, there's also a risk. The potential of its domestic majoritarian impulses clashing with global pluralistic ideals could undermine India's aspirations on the world stage. As the world becomes more interconnected, understanding the nuances of this interplay between India's religious nationalism and its international ambitions is not just crucial for India, but for the global community at large. This paper seeks to delve into this intricate relationship, exploring the multifaceted ways in which religious nationalism in India shapes, and is shaped by, its interactions with the world.

2 Historical Context of Religious Nationalism in India

Religious nationalism, where faith and national identity converge, has been an integral force in India's multifaceted history, shaping both its internal dynamics and its interactions on the global stage. India, with its myriad traditions and spiritual practices, has always been a crucible of religious influences, but the deliberate fusion of religion with politics, especially in the form of Hindu nationalism, has its roots firmly embedded in the colonial epoch [8].

2.1 Colonial Catalysts and Emergence of Hindu Nationalism

The late 19th and early 20th centuries, under the shadow of British colonialism, witnessed a resurgence in indigenous socio-religious movements. Groups such as the Arya Samaj and the Ramakrishna Mission emerged not merely as spiritual endeavors but also as sociopolitical movements that instilled a renewed sense of pride in India's Hindu heritage, setting the stage for the emergence of Hindu nationalism [9, 10]. In the 1920s, the establishment of the Rashtriya Swayamsevak Sangh (RSS) marked a pivotal turn. Conceived as a cultural organization, the RSS aimed to create a robust Hindu society, emphasizing physical fitness, discipline, and moral strength. While its initial years were focused on cultural rejuvenation, it soon became a political force, laying the foundation for parties like the Bharatiya Jana Sangh and its successor, the Bharatiya Janata Party (BJP) [11].

2.2 The Partition and its Repercussions

The trauma of the 1947 Partition, which saw the Indian subcontinent being cleaved into Hindu-majority India and Muslim-majority Pakistan, was a cataclysmic event that intensified religious fervor. This division, rooted in religious differences, fostered deep-seated animosities and further fortified religious identities. Subsequent

wars, disputes over Kashmir, and regional tensions kept the religious cauldron simmering, further entrenching religious nationalism within political discourse.

2.3 The Ayodhya Dispute and the Rise of the BJP

The late 20th century witnessed religious nationalism becoming mainstream. The BJP and its affiliates championed the cause of the Ram temple at Ayodhya, galvanizing vast sections of Hindus and deepening communal divides. The 1992 demolition of the Babri Masjid and the ensuing riots were stark manifestations of the influence of religious nationalism.

2.4 BJP's Evolution in the 21st Century

With the dawn of the new millennium, the BJP emerged as a central force in Indian politics. Leaders like Vajpayee and Modi managed to combine the party's religious nationalist agenda with broader governance issues, making it more palatable to a diverse electorate. Their emphasis on development, while retaining the core Hindu nationalist principles, allowed the BJP to achieve significant electoral victories, further mainstreaming religious nationalism.

2.5 Religious Nationalism and India's International Relations

The influence of religious nationalism is not confined to India's borders. It has significantly impacted India's foreign policy, influencing its relationships with neighbors and defining its stance on global issues. The country's dealings with Pakistan, its approach to the Kashmir issue, and its broader strategy in the South Asian region are all viewed through the prism of religious nationalism.

The journey of religious nationalism in India, from the colonial-era reform movements to its central role in contemporary politics, offers profound insights into the nation's soul. The interplay between religion, politics, and identity, against the backdrop of historical events and charismatic leaders, paints a vivid tapestry of a nation in constant evolution, grappling with its diverse past while charting a path for the future.

3 Literature Review

The interplay between diasporas and foreign relations has long been a topic of scholarly attention. Brubaker [12] posits that diasporas, as transnational communities, can exert significant influence on the foreign policies of their host nations. This is particularly evident in countries with significant immigrant populations, where diaspora communities can leverage their dual identities to bridge their homeland and host nation [13]. The Sikh diaspora in Canada serves as a prime example of this dynamic, with its ability to influence Canadian policies toward India [14].

Canada-India relations, historically characterized by trade and mutual cooperation, have seen sporadic tensions, often rooted in domestic issues that spill over onto the international stage [15]. As noted by Nayar [16], while the two nations share democratic values and a British colonial history, differences in their perceptions of regional security issues, particularly concerning Sikh separatist movements, have been a point of contention. The Khalistan movement, which advocates for a separate Sikh state in India, has been a significant source of strain, with India frequently expressing concerns about pro-Khalistan sentiments among Sikh Canadians [17].

The intersection of domestic politics and foreign policy becomes especially evident when analyzing the influence of international incidents on bilateral trade relations. Trade relations, while ideally rooted in economic considerations, often become intertwined with political issues, leading to disruptions. Gowa and Mansfield [18] assert that political conflicts can substantially impact trade flows, even in the absence of formal sanctions. This is evident in the recent Canada-India tensions, where political disagreements have led to halts in trade negotiations and affected specific industries.

Additionally, the role of intelligence-sharing alliances in international diplomacy has been highlighted by scholars [19]. The "Five Eyes" alliance, consisting of the U.S., the U.K., Canada, Australia, and New Zealand, underscores the importance of shared intelligence in shaping diplomatic responses to international incidents. Such alliances can act as force multipliers, reinforcing the stances of individual member nations and presenting a unified front in global affairs [20].

In conclusion, the existing literature underscores the complexity of Canada-India relations, influenced by the dynamics of the Sikh diaspora, historical and contemporary political issues, and the broader geopolitical landscape. This literature sets the stage for an in-depth analysis of the recent incident involving the assassination of Hardeep Singh Nijjar and its ripple effects on bilateral relations.

4 Fraying India-Canada Relations Over Sikh Separatist's Killing

The intricate tapestry of international relations is often woven with threads of historical ties, economic interdependence, and mutual interests. However, just as often, it is punctuated by knots of misunderstandings, disagreements, and incidents that challenge the very fabric of these relationships. One such knot that has emerged prominently in recent times is the rapidly deteriorating relationship between Canada and India, two nations that, historically, have enjoyed a relatively amicable rapport anchored by trade and the significant Indian diaspora in Canada. Yet, as the events surrounding the assassination of Sikh separatist leader Hardeep Singh Nijjar in Vancouver reveal, even longstanding ties can be tested. This incident, deeply rooted in the sensitivities surrounding the Khalistan movement and Sikh activism in Canada, has led to a cascade of diplomatic confrontations, public accusations, and economic repercussions. As Canadian Prime Minister Justin Trudeau and Indian Prime Minister Narendra Modi exchanged barbs on international platforms, it became evident that beneath the surface of trade agreements and diplomatic visits, there lay simmering tensions waiting for a spark. This case study endeavors to unpack the multi-faceted dimensions of this complex situation, tracing the events, reactions, and potential future implications for both nations and the world at large.

4.1 Historical Context

Understanding the current tensions between Canada and India requires delving into the deep-rooted historical context that has, over time, shaped the dynamics between the two nations. Central to this historical narrative is the Sikh community, which has played a pivotal role in influencing the socio-political fabric of both countries.

4.2 The Significance of the Sikh Population in Canada

Canada is home to the world's largest Sikh population outside of India, with nearly 770,000 individuals, making up 2.1% of the nation's populace. Their presence has not only enriched the multicultural tapestry of Canada but has also paved the way for active political participation. This was evident when, in 2015, Canadian Prime Minister Justin Trudeau appointed four Sikh ministers to his then 30-member cabinet, a testament to the community's integration and influence in Canadian politics.

4.3 Past Instances of Concerns

The historical ties between India and Canada have not been without their challenges. Tensions between the two nations began to surface in 2015, when Canadian Prime Minister Justin Trudeau, after coming to power, appointed four Sikh ministers to his 30-member cabinet. This move was viewed with skepticism by some Indian officials, who expressed concerns about potential support for the Khalistan movement among Sikh Canadians. These concerns were exacerbated when incidents like the vandalism of a Hindu temple in Canada with graffiti reading "death to India" in Urdu and "Khalistan" occurred, and when local referendums were organized by Sikh Canadians advocating for Sikh independence from India. Trudeau's 2018 visit to India further highlighted these underlying tensions when his delegation, which included a Sikh contingent, encountered criticism for meeting with Jaspal Atwal, a Sikh individual convicted of attempting to murder a visiting Indian cabinet minister.

4.4 The Khalistan Movement and its Implications in Canada-India Relations

The Khalistan movement, which advocates for a separate Sikh homeland carved out of the northern Indian state of Punjab, has long been a point of contention in India-Canada relations. While the movement's origins trace back to colonial-era grievances, its modern iteration gained momentum in the 1980s and early 1990s in India, leading to violent clashes and a tragic episode in Indian history, the 1984 anti-Sikh riots. While the movement's intensity has diminished in India over the years, its echoes have reverberated in countries with significant Sikh diasporas, including Canada. Over the years, some sections of the Sikh community in Canada have continued to express support for the Khalistan cause, leading to concerns in India about Canada being used as a platform for anti-India activities. The recent assassination of Hardeep Singh Nijjar, a vocal supporter of the Khalistan movement, has reignited these concerns and added a new dimension to the already strained relationship between the two countries.

4.5 The Incident: Hardeep Singh Nijjar's Assassination

Hardeep Singh Nijjar, a prominent figure within certain circles of the Sikh community in Canada, was not just another expatriate. He was notably labeled as the head of the Khalistani Tiger Force (KTF), a pro-Khalistan group. This designation was not without consequence; India had officially labeled him a "terrorist" three years

prior to his assassination. Despite residing in Canada, Nijjar's activities and affiliations kept him on India's radar due to concerns about the resurgence of the Khalistan movement and its potential implications for India's internal security.

The fatal incident occurred on June 18, when Nijjar was leaving a Sikh gurdwara in a Vancouver suburb. Two masked gunmen approached and shot him, ending the life of a figure who had been at the center of many controversies between India and Canada.

The assassination of Hardeep Singh Nijjar was not treated as a mere criminal act by the Canadian authorities. Given his high-profile status and the political implications of his death, the investigation took on a broader dimension. Canadian Prime Minister Justin Trudeau, in an unprecedented move, publicly announced suspicions that agents of the Indian government might have been involved in the killing. This assertion was based on "credible allegations" even as investigations were still underway.

This assassination and its subsequent allegations did not remain a bilateral issue for long. Canada's intelligence community sought external validation by sharing evidence with partners in the "Five Eyes" intelligence alliance. This alliance, comprising the U.S., the U.K., Canada, Australia, and New Zealand, is one of the most comprehensive intelligence collaborations globally. Reports emerged that some leaders from these countries had discussed the issue with Indian Prime Minister Narendra Modi during the G-20 summit, indicating the gravity of the situation.

Additionally, Canadian National Security Adviser (NSA) Jody Thomas made two trips to India within a month of the incident, aiming to discuss the case with India's NSA, Ajit Doval. The continuous engagement and high-level discussions underscored the significant impact of this single event on the broader canvas of Canada-India relations.

4.6 Diplomatic Fallout

Canadian Prime Minister Justin Trudeau's public announcement in the Canadian Parliament was a defining moment in the diplomatic relations between Canada and India. By voicing suspicions that Indian government agents might have played a role in Nijjar's assassination, Trudeau set the stage for heightened tensions. This move was especially notable given that the investigation into the assassination was still ongoing. Such a public declaration from the leader of a nation has far-reaching implications, suggesting a significant level of trust erosion and suspicion between the two nations.

The G-20 summit in New Delhi shortly after the incident became a platform for bilateral discussions on the issue. On the sidelines of this summit, both leaders had a stormy bilateral "pull-aside" meeting. While both countries pointed fingers at each other, accusing one another of "foreign interference" and "providing safe havens to anti-India extremists", the assassination of Nijjar loomed large in their discussions, even if it was not publicly acknowledged at that time. In a swift and significant reaction to Trudeau's comments, the Canadian government expelled a senior Indian diplomat. India, not to be outdone, retaliated by expelling an unnamed senior Canadian diplomat. Such tit-for-tat expulsions underscored the deteriorating trust and escalating tensions between the two nations. These actions were not just symbolic; they reflected a deeper strain in diplomatic relations, with potential consequences for various bilateral initiatives and collaborations.

The "Five Eyes" intelligence alliance's involvement added another layer to the diplomatic fallout. Reports suggested that Canada had shared evidence with its "Five Eyes" partners prior to the G-20 summit. Consequently, some of their leaders, equipped with this shared intelligence, reportedly discussed the issue with Prime Minister Modi. The engagement of this intelligence alliance indicated the gravity with which the matter was being treated, not just by Canada but by several major Western powers. Their involvement potentially risked complicating the situation further, adding multilateral dimensions to what was initially a bilateral dispute.

4.7 Economic and Trade Implications

The economic ties between India and Canada, once promising, faced significant disruptions due to the evolving diplomatic tensions. On September 1, Canada took the unexpected step of pausing talks on the proposed trade treaty with India. This decision, coming just three months after both nations expressed intentions to finalize an initial agreement within the year, was a clear indication of the extent to which political tensions could impact economic engagements. Further emphasizing the strained relations, Canada postponed a significant trade mission to India planned for October. Such missions, typically aimed at fostering business ties and exploring investment opportunities, play a crucial role in deepening economic relations. The postponement, attributed to concerns surrounding Nijjar's assassination, manifested the apprehensions on the Canadian side and their potential long-term impact on trade relations. Several industries became the immediate casualties of the diplomatic rift:

1. **Steel:** India's JSW Steel Ltd began slowing down its process to purchase a stake in the coal unit of Canada's Teck Resources. Even though India's steel secretary later mentioned that Indian exports to Canada were marginal and unaffected, the hesitation shown by major companies signaled concerns in the business community.
2. **Potash:** Amid the tensions, the fertiliser importer Indian Potash maintained its expectation that the supplies of Canadian potash would remain unaffected. India hoped to extend its contract with the Canadian supplier Canpotex beyond September. Given that Canada is a primary supplier of potash to India, any disruption in this trade could have significant implications for India's agricultural sector.
3. **Lentils:** Canadian lentil sales to India, a staple in the Indian diet, slowed down due to the diplomatic tensions. With Canada serving as India's main source for lentil imports, any long-term disruption in this trade could affect prices and availability in the Indian market.

These industry-specific implications underscored the intertwined nature of economic and diplomatic relations, demonstrating that political disputes could have tangible effects on the ground, affecting businesses and consumers alike.

4.8 International Reactions and Implications

The diplomatic tensions between India and Canada drew attention from the global community, with several countries voicing their concerns and positions on the matter:

1. **United States:** The U.S. National Security Council spokesperson, Adrienne Watson, expressed deep concerns about the allegations raised by Canada regarding Nijjar's assassination. The White House emphasized the importance of a thorough investigation and the need to bring the perpetrators to justice. The U.S. stance showcased its balancing act, maintaining good relations with both India and Canada.
2. **Australia and Britain:** Both nations echoed concerns over the killing of Nijjar. Their responses were indicative of the shared interests and concerns within the "Five Eyes" intelligence alliance, which also includes Canada, New Zealand, and the U.S. Their collective apprehension further intensified the spotlight on the issue.

4.9 The India-Canada dispute had broader implications for the geopolitics of the Indo-Pacific region:

- **The China Factor:** With both India and Canada having past tensions with China, their bilateral relationship was seen by many analysts as a potential counterweight to Beijing's influence in the region. However, the diplomatic fallout risked undermining this potential alliance, with Derek J. Grossman from the RAND Corporation highlighting the challenge for the Biden Administration in taking a stand without alienating either party. The primary objective, as Grossman noted, was to keep India aligned with Western interests, especially in countering China through the Indo-Pacific strategy.
- **Regional Alliances and Partnerships:** The diplomatic spat threatened to reshape alliances and partnerships in the region. India's growing importance in the Indo-Pacific strategy, especially its role in the Quad (comprising the U.S., India, Japan, and Australia), meant that any prolonged tension with Canada could have ripple effects on regional collaborations and strategies.

In conclusion, the India-Canada diplomatic crisis not only affected their bilateral relations but also had the potential to reshape the geopolitical landscape of the Indo-Pacific, influencing decisions and alignments of various major global players.

4.10 Analysis: The Role of Diasporas in Foreign Relations

Diasporas have historically played a pivotal role in shaping the foreign policies of their adopted nations, with their influence stemming from their numbers, economic contributions, and sometimes, their involvement in domestic politics. The Sikh community in Canada and its impact on Canada-India relations offers a prime example.

1. **Influence of the Sikh Community in Canada:** Significant Population: Canada is home to the largest Sikh population outside India, comprising nearly 770,000 individuals or about 2.1% of the country's population. This sizeable community has a strong voice and can influence domestic politics, especially in areas with a high Sikh concentration.

2. **Political Representation:** The political clout of the Sikh community in Canada became evident when Prime Minister Trudeau appointed four Sikh ministers to his 30-member cabinet in 2015. Such representation further empowers the diaspora to influence decisions that pertain to their homeland.
3. **Cultural and Security Concerns:** The Khalistan movement, advocating for a separate Sikh homeland in India, has found resonance among some sections of the Sikh diaspora in Canada. Events such as the vandalism of a Hindu temple in Canada with pro-Khalistan graffiti and local referendums on Sikh independence are indicative of these undercurrents. Such activities can strain relations between their home and host countries, as seen in the current Canada-India dispute.

4.11 Comparisons with Other Diaspora-Driven Foreign Policy Decisions

Diasporas have historically influenced the foreign policies of their host nations. Their contributions in the form of remittances, cultural exchanges, and political lobbying often make them key stakeholders in bilateral relations. Here are a few notable instances where diaspora communities have significantly impacted foreign policy decisions:

1. **Armenian Diaspora and the U.S.:** The U.S. is home to a significant Armenian community, which has, over the years, actively lobbied for the recognition of the Armenian Genocide by the Ottoman Turks during World War I. Their consistent efforts eventually led to the U.S. Congress officially recognizing the Armenian Genocide in 2019. This decision, influenced in large part by the Armenian diaspora, notably strained U.S.-Turkey relations.
2. **Cuban-Americans and U.S. Policy on Cuba:** Cuban-Americans, primarily residing in Florida, have played a pivotal role in shaping U.S. policies towards Cuba. Historically anti-Castro and anti-communist, this influential diaspora has been a driving force behind the U.S.'s continued embargo against Cuba and its hardline stance against the Cuban government.
3. **Jewish Diaspora and Israel:** Jewish communities, especially in the U.S. and Europe, have significantly influenced policies in favor of Israel. Through powerful lobbying groups and a network of supporters, they've managed to secure diplomatic backing, foreign aid, and military support for Israel. Their influence has played a role in decisions such as the U.S.'s recognition of Jerusalem as the capital of Israel.
4. **Indian Diaspora in the U.S.:** The Indian community in the U.S. has grown in influence and has been instrumental in fostering closer U.S.-India ties. Their role in facilitating the U.S.-India nuclear deal, promoting business partnerships, and advocating for strategic cooperation showcases their impact.

In each of these instances, diaspora communities have used their collective influence, financial power, and political connections to shape decisions that resonate deeply with their cultural and historical identities. These cases underscore the importance of diasporas as active participants in the foreign policy domain, capable of bridging their homeland's interests with those of their adopted nations.

4.12 Moving Forward: Potential Pathways to Resolution

The recent tensions between Canada and India, rooted in the tragic assassination of Hardeep Singh Nijjar and exacerbated by historical issues surrounding the Sikh diaspora, have undeniably strained bilateral relations. However, history has shown that nations can find pathways to rebuild and strengthen ties, even after significant disagreements.

4.13 Analysis of Statements and Actions Post-Incident:

Post the assassination incident, both countries have expressed concerns, taken decisive actions, and made official statements that reflect their stances. Canada's Prime Minister Justin Trudeau publicly aired suspicions of Indian involvement, which led to diplomatic expulsions from both sides. On the other hand, India has vehemently denied any role in the incident and expressed concerns about Sikh separatist activities in Canada. While these actions and statements seem confrontational, they also indicate an underlying desire in both nations to address and resolve the root issues.

Recommendations and Potential Avenues for Repairing the Relationship:

- **Bilateral Talks:** Engaging in open dialogue is paramount. Both countries should initiate high-level bilateral talks to address their concerns. Establishing a joint investigation team for Nijjar's assassination could be a starting point.

- **Diaspora Engagement:** Canada could set up platforms for the Sikh community to voice their concerns and aspirations. This will provide insights into the community's perspectives and help in understanding the root causes of any extremist sentiments.
- **Trade and Economic Cooperation:** Both countries should aim to separate trade relations from political disputes. Renewing talks on the suspended trade treaty and focusing on mutual economic benefits can be a soft power approach to rebuilding trust.
- **Cultural and Educational Exchanges:** Enhancing people-to-people ties through student exchange programs, cultural festivals, and collaborative research can foster goodwill and mutual understanding.
- **Third-party Mediation:** If bilateral talks face challenges, seeking mediation or facilitation from a neutral third-party country or international body might be beneficial.
- **Review of Diplomatic Expulsions:** A gesture of goodwill could be to reconsider the decision on the expelled diplomats, fostering a more conducive environment for dialogue.
- **Engage in Multilateral Forums:** Joint participation in international forums, where both nations can work towards common global goals, might help in diffusing bilateral tensions.

In conclusion, while the current situation between India and Canada is fraught with challenges, the historical ties and shared values between the two democracies provide a foundation upon which trust can be rebuilt. With mutual respect, open dialogue, and a focus on shared interests, both nations can navigate this turbulent phase and forge a stronger, more resilient bilateral relationship.

The recent tensions between Canada and India surrounding the assassination of Hardeep Singh Nijjar serve as a poignant reminder of the intricate and delicate nature of international diplomacy, especially in an era of global interconnectedness. While the immediate ramifications have been palpable, with both nations experiencing strained diplomatic and trade ties, the long-term implications could be even more profound. Such incidents underscore the importance of mutual understanding, continuous dialogue, and respect for sovereignty. Moreover, in an age where diasporas play a pivotal role in shaping foreign relations, nations must be adept at navigating the dual challenges of domestic considerations and international obligations. The Canada-India episode offers broader lessons for the global community: in an interconnected world, nations must act with heightened sensitivity, always striving for collaborative solutions that uphold the principles of mutual respect and trust.

5 Discussion

The recent diplomatic tensions between Canada and India, instigated by the assassination of Hardeep Singh Nijjar, offer an intricate view into the multifaceted dynamics of international relations. This incident, far from being an isolated event, is emblematic of the interplay between domestic politics, international diplomacy, and diasporic influences. The influence of the Sikh diaspora in Canada is undeniable. Their significant presence and active participation in Canadian politics make them essential stakeholders in Canada-India bilateral relations. Over the years, diasporas worldwide, be it the Cuban-Americans influencing U.S.-Cuba relations or the Armenian-Americans shaping U.S.-Armenia ties, have showcased their potential to be pressure points in international diplomacy. Their dual identities, rooted both in their adopted and ancestral lands, can often lead to nations making decisions that might not always align with overarching diplomatic strategies, but instead resonate with the sentiments of these influential communities. While trade and economic interdependence have historically been seen as buffers during diplomatic tensions, the Canada-India fallout has demonstrated the vulnerability of such ties. The suspension of crucial trade negotiations, combined with the impact on specific sectors like steel, potash, and lentils, indicates the depth of the rift. Such economic repercussions not only affect the immediate stakeholders but can also have cascading effects on global supply chains and trade dynamics. The global community's reactions, especially from significant players like the United States, Australia, and Britain, highlight the extensive implications of the Canada-India dispute. In an era of shifting power dynamics, with China emerging as a dominant force in the Indo-Pacific, democratic countries are increasingly feeling the need for strengthened alliances. Any fracture in these alliances, as the Canada-India dispute might suggest, can alter the balance of power in the region. The involvement of the "Five Eyes" intelligence alliance adds another layer of complexity. Intelligence sharing and covert operations often underpin international relations, and in situations like these, they can either be instruments of resolution or further discord.

6 Conclusion

The unfolding of events following the assassination of Hardeep Singh Nijjar has provided a window into the intricate dance of international diplomacy. In an interconnected world, bilateral tensions are rarely isolated; they reverberate, affecting a network of intertwined relationships. The Canada-India incident underscores the growing influence of diasporas in shaping international narratives. As nations grapple with the challenges of catering to both domestic and international audiences, the role of diasporas in bridging or widening gaps becomes crucial. Furthermore, the economic ramifications of the dispute highlight the intertwined nature of global economies. While economic partnerships are often celebrated as markers of strong bilateral ties, they can also become points of contention during disagreements. Lastly, in the larger geopolitical arena, bilateral disputes can have implications that go beyond immediate concerns. As nations form alliances and counter-alliances, the stability of these groupings becomes paramount for regional and global stability. For Canada and India, the road to reconciliation will require a delicate balance of understanding historical contexts, addressing immediate concerns, and having an eye on the broader regional implications. Their shared democratic values provide a foundation upon which trust can be rebuilt, but the journey will require patience, dialogue, and mutual respect. This expanded discussion and conclusion should provide a more comprehensive understanding of the topic's complexities and implications.

References

- [1] Christophe Jaffrelot. *Modi's India: Hindu nationalism and the rise of ethnic democracy*. Princeton University Press, 2021.
- [2] Giorgio Shani. Towards a hindu rashtra: Hindutva, religion, and nationalism in india. *Religion, State & Society*, 49(3):264–280, 2021.
- [3] Mark Juergensmeyer. The clash of religious politics in india. *Nation, Nationalism and the Public Sphere: Religious Politics in India*. New Delhi: SAGE, pages 17–36, 2020.
- [4] Niladri Chatterjee, Zaad Mahmood, and Eleonor Marcussen. Politics of vaccine nationalism in india: global and domestic implications. In *Forum for Development Studies*, volume 48, pages 357–369. Taylor & Francis, 2021.
- [5] Neelanjan Sircar. The politics of vishwas: Political mobilization in the 2019 national election. *Contemporary South Asia*, 28(2):178–194, 2020.
- [6] Thomas Blom Hansen and Srirupa Roy. *Saffron Republic: Hindu Nationalism and State Power in India*. Cambridge University Press, 2022.
- [7] Jeff Kingston. *The politics of religion, nationalism, and identity in Asia*. Rowman & Littlefield, 2019.
- [8] Simon Ozer. Globalization and radicalization: A cross-national study of local embeddedness and reactions to cultural globalization in regard to violent extremism. *International Journal of Intercultural Relations*, 76:26–36, 2020.
- [9] Sophie-Jung H Kim. The global turn in nationalism: The usa as a battleground for hinduism and hindu nationalism. *Religions*, 14(10):1265, 2023.
- [10] Bishnupriya Ghosh. The making of the hindu normative. *boundary 2*, 50(2):211–222, 2023.
- [11] Marium Fatima, Ghulam Ali Murtaza, and Arshi Saleem Hashmi. Rise of right-wing indian nationalism: Implications for south asia. *Margalla Papers*, 23(2), 2019.
- [12] Rogers Brubaker. The ‘diaspora’ diaspora. *Ethnic and racial studies*, 28(1):1–19, 2005.
- [13] Mari Toivanen and Bahar Baser. Diasporas’ multiple roles in peace and conflict: A review of current debates. *Migration letters*, 17(1):47–57, 2020.
- [14] Sameer Patil. Partnering for prosperity: India-canada collaboration to curb digital black markets. 2019.
- [15] Elizabeth P Anderson, Sue Jackson, Rebecca E Tharme, Michael Douglas, Joseph E Flotemersch, Margreet Zwartveen, Chicu Lokgariwar, Mariana Montoya, Alaka Wali, Gail T Tipa, et al. Understanding rivers and their social relations: A critical step to advance environmental water management. *Wiley Interdisciplinary Reviews: Water*, 6(6):e1381, 2019.

- [16] Raviraj Shetty and Shoba Nayar. Understanding the person-occupation enmeshment through exploring the erosion of tribal occupations in india. *Journal of Occupational Science*, pages 1–14, 2023.
- [17] Valerie A Wright-St Clair and Shoba Nayar. Resettling amidst a mood of loneliness: later-life chinese, indian and korean immigrants in new zealand. *Ageing & Society*, 40(11):2393–2409, 2020.
- [18] Joanne Gowa and Edward D Mansfield. Power politics and international trade. *American political science review*, 87(2):408–420, 1993.
- [19] Panagiotis Fragkos, Heleen Laura van Soest, Roberto Schaeffer, Luke Reedman, Alexandre C Köberle, Nick Macaluso, Stavroula Evangelopoulou, Alessia De Vita, Fu Sha, Chai Qimin, et al. Energy system transitions and low-carbon pathways in australia, brazil, canada, china, eu-28, india, indonesia, japan, republic of korea, russia and the united states. *Energy*, 216:119385, 2021.
- [20] Mohammad Mafizur Rahman and Xuan-Binh Vu. The nexus between renewable energy, economic growth, trade, urbanisation and environmental quality: A comparative study for australia and canada. *Renewable Energy*, 155:617–627, 2020.